

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of 2-substituted benzyl hydrazino-3-methyl quinoxalines

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Reduction of 3-methyl-2-(arylidene hydrazino)quinoxalines 5a-l with NaBH₄ in controlled experimental conditions to give the 2-substituted benzyl hydrazine-3-methyl quinoxalines 6a-l have been described. The structure of compounds 6a-l have been confirmed from elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data. All the compounds have been screened for their antimicrobial activity against several microbes.

Hydrazone exhibit various biological activities^{1,2}. Several diazo, hydrazine derivative are also found to be good CNS active oxidase inhibitor^{3,4} and antibacterial agents⁵⁻⁷. On the other hand compounds having quinoxaline nuclei have been reported to show a variety of biological activities⁸. A study on the influence of structure on the activity shows that some times a minor change in the heterocyclic nuclei enhances the pharmacological profile many fold than the parent nuclei. With a view to assess the potential of hydrazine derivatives of type 6a-l, we report here in the synthesis and antimicrobial effect of some new 2-substituted benzyl hydrazino-3-methyl quinoxalines.

The sequence of reactions followed in the synthesis of designed compounds is depicted in the following.

The target 2-hydrazino-3-methyl quinoxaline was prepared by the treatment of chlorocompound and hydrazine hydrate in ethanol, which on condensation with aromatic aldehydes yield 3-methyl-2-(arylidene hydrazine) quinoxalines 5a-l. Compounds 5 on reduction with sodium borohydride as per reported method⁹ yield 2-substituted benzyl hydrazino-3-methyl quinoxalines 6a-l (Scheme 1) (Table 1).

All the products 6a-l have been characterized by elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral studies. All the compounds have been screened for their antimicrobial activity against different strains of bacteria and fungi.

Results and discussion

IR spectrum of compound 4 shows a sharp doublet at 3286 and 3188 due to the NH str. of NH₂. Compound 4 on

Scheme 1

condensation with carbonyl compound these bands disappear and a band at 3298 cm⁻¹ is observed due to NH str. The ¹H NMR spectrum of compound 4 shows a broad signal at δ 4.25 due to NH₂ protons and at δ 6.5 the characteristics of NH proton. The compound, on condensation with carbonyl compound the hydrazones formed, shows disappearance of NH₂ protons signal, while that of NH proton signal are shifted up field at δ 9.12 as a result of deshielding effect of HC=N- group. The proton of azomethine (-N=CH-) group leads to a sharp singlet at δ 8.4. Sharp signal appears at δ 3.93, the characteristics of protons of -OCH₃. Similarly a sharp signal at δ 2.27 is characteristics of protons of -CH₃. In all the compounds a sharp singlet at δ 2.6 is due to the protons of -CH₃ attached to the hetero nucleus (quinoxaline ring). There is a sharp signal at δ 3.97 the characteristics of protons of -CH₂ group and disappearance of signal at δ 8.4, indicating the reduction of CH=N group of hydrazones.

Table 1. NMR spectral data of compounds 6a-l

Compd.	R	M.p. (°C)	X	CH ₂	Ar-H
6a	C ₆ H ₅ -	163	-	3.91 (CH, s)	7.0-8.1 (9H, m)
6b	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	174	-	3.94 (CH, s)	7.1-8.2 (8H, m)
6c	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	152	-	3.91 (CH, s)	7.1-8.1 (8H, m)
6d	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	148	-	3.98 (CH, s)	7.0-7.9 (8H, m)
6e	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	168	-	3.93 (CH, s)	7.0-7.9 (8H, m)
6f	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	140	-	3.95 (CH, s)	6.9-7.9 (8H, m)
6g	2-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ -	210	3.98 (3H, s)	3.96 (CH, s)	7.1-8.4 (7H, m)
6h	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ -	185	3.99 (3H, s)	3.97 (CH, s)	7.3-8.4 (7H, m)
6i	2-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	176	3.62 (3H, s)	3.96 (CH, s)	7.4-8.5 (7H, m)
6j	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	185	3.92 (3H, s)	3.97 (CH, s)	7.0-8.1 (8H, m)
6k	C ₄ H ₃ O-	187	-	3.91 (CH, s)	7.1-8.2 (7H, m)
6l	C ₆ H ₄ -CH=CH-	152	-	3.96 (CH, s)	7.3-8.2 (8H, m)

Table 2. Antimicrobial data (inhibition zones 16-25 mm) of some selected compds. which exhibited highest activity

Standard	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>B. serus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
Antibiotics					
Ampicillin	6a, 6c, 6k	6b, 6g, 6i	6b, 6f, 6k	6a, 6c, 6d, 6k	6b, 6f, 6g
15-25 mm					
Chloramphenicol					
15-28 mm					
Penicillin					
18-23 mm					
Greseofulvin					
15-20 mm					

All the compounds reported in the Table 1 were tested *in vitro* for their antimicrobial activity against various microbes. Under identical conditions, the standard antibiotics showed zone of inhibitions like ampicillin 15-26 mm, chloramphenicol 15-18 mm, penicillin 18-23 mm against bacterial strain and greseofulvin 15-20 mm showed zone of inhibition against *A. niger*.

It can be concluded from the Table 2 that the compounds 6a, 6c, 6k were highly active against *Bacillus subtilis*. The compounds 6b, 6g and 6i showed significant activity against *Bacillus serus* and 6a, 6c, 6d and 6k were active against *Pseudomonas*. The other compounds showed either moderate or less activity against these organisms. In the case of *Escherichia coli*, 6b, 6f and 6k compounds have showed maximum activity. The compounds 6b, 6f and 6g showed highest activity against *Aspergillus niger*.

In vitro evaluation of pharmacological studies :

The antimicrobial activity was assayed by using the cup-plate agar diffusion method^{10,11}, by measuring the inhibition zones in mm. All the compounds were screened *in vitro* for their antimicrobial activity against variety of bacterial strains such as *Escherichia coli*, and *Aspergillus*

niger at a concentration of 40 µg. Known antibiotics like chloramphenicol, ampicillin, penicillin and greseofulvin were used for comparison purpose.

Experimental

All the recorded melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR (KBr disc) spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu FT-IR-8400 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra on Bruker spectrometer (300 Mz) using TMS as an internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer. The elemental analysis of the synthesized products have been done at M. S. University, Baroda.

Preparation of 2-hydrazino-3-methyl quinoxaline (4) : *o*-Phenylenediamine (0.01 mol) and ethyl pyruvate (0.01 mol) were mixed in dry benzene to yield 2-hydroxy-3-methyl quinoxaline which (0.01 mol) on treatment with phosphorus oxychloride (6 ml) yielded 2-chloro-3-methyl quinoxaline. The chlorocompound (0.015 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol 99%) in ethanol (25 ml) refluxed for 3 h to yield 2-hydrazino-3-methyl quinoxaline. The product was recrystallised with ethanol to give the pure compound. 4 : yield 92.5%, m.p. 172°C (Found : C, 62.25; H, 5.92; N,

32.01. C₉H₁₀N₄ requires : C, 62.05; H, 5.78; N, 31.17%); IR (KBr disc) 3288 and 3186 (doublet for NH of NH₂), 1625 (C=N str.), 1573 (-NH def.), 1191 cm⁻¹ (-C-N str.); ¹H NMR δ in (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.52 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.25 (2H, br, NH₂, D₂O exchangeable), 6.2 (1H, br, NH), 7.74 and 7.86 (2H, d, quinoxaline ring protons), 7.43 and 7.56 (2H, t, quinoxaline ring protons); ¹³C NMR δ 127.98 (d, C-5), 127.52 (d, C-6), 129.62 (d, C-7), 129.69 (d, C-8), 140.36 (s, C-9), 141.18 (s, C-10), 147.02 (s, C-2), 152.00 (s, C-3) carbon atoms of quinoxaline moiety and δ 22.83 (quartet) of methyl carbon on C-2.

Preparation of 3-methyl-2-(arylidene hydrazine) quinoxaline (5) : A mixture of compound 4 (0.01 mol) and *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in methanol was refluxed for 6 h. The product separated was isolated and neutralized with sodium bisulphite to get 3-methyl-2-(4'-methoxy benzylidene)hydrazino quinoxaline. yield 85%, m.p. 185°C (Found : C, 65.99; H, 5.15; N, 18.10. C₁₇H₁₆N₄O₂ requires : C, 66.23; H, 5.19; N, 18.18%); IR (KBr disc) 3540 (-NH str.), 1600 (C=N str.), 1541 (NH def.) 1166 (C-N str.) and 1040 cm⁻¹ (-C-OCH₃); ¹H NMR δ in (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.62 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.95 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.85 and 6.95 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz part of A₂B₂ system of protons from methoxy containing aryl ring), 7.0 and 7.25 (2H, d, quinoxaline ring protons), 7.2 and 7.35 (2H, t, quinoxaline ring protons), 7.75 and 7.85 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz part of A₂B₂ system of protons from methoxy containing aryl ring), 8.4 (1H, s, N=CH-) and 9.12 (1H, s, -NH-N); MS [FAB], *m/z* 309.

Preparation of 2-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxy benzyl hydrazino)-3-methyl quinoxalines (6h) : Sodium borohydride (0.03 *M*) was added to the methanolic solution of 3-methyl-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxy benzylidene hydrazine) quinoxaline (0.02 *M*) over a period of 30 min at a temperatures 5–10°C. The reaction mixture was then kept over night at room temperature. The excess of borohydride was neutralized by adding water and the product was extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water until neutral and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and finally the ether was evaporated to give the hydrazine derivative 2-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxy benzyl hydrazino)-3-methyl quinoxaline. the product isolated. Yield 50%, m.p. 145°C (Found : C, 65.50; H, 5.82; N, 18.12. C₁₇H₁₈N₄O₂ requires : C, 65.08; H, 5.80; N, 18.06%); IR (KBr disc) 3361 (-NH str.), 1660 (C=N str.), 1577 (NH def.), 1184 (C-N str.), 1040 (-C-OCH₃); ¹H NMR δ in (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.57 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.97 (2H, s, -CH₂), 3.99

(3H, s, OCH₃), 6.2–7.9 (3H, m, ArH), 7.43 and 7.56 (2H, t, quinoxaline ring protons), 7.74 and 7.86 (2H, d, quinoxaline ring protons), 8.2 and 8.6 (2H, br, -NH-NH-); MS [FAB], *m/z* 310. Similarly other members of compounds 5 were reduced with sodium borohydride to give the corresponding hydrazine derivatives 6.

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